

Discretized Radon Transform and its Spectral Properties

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ABSTRACT

The sampling theorem also known as Shannon theorem is the basis for digital signal processing and computer based algorithms. A great number of publications is devoted to sampling and reconstruction of signals [3] [4]. Spectral properties of the underlying continuous signals and different kinds of applications require a specific approach in designing an optimal sampling grid. For doing this, in the domain of multidimensional signal processing a greater degree of freedom can be utilized. In this paper the spectral properties of the projection signal of a tomograph with respect to the bandwidth is analysed and an optimal sampling grid for projection data is presented.

1 Introduction

In medical imaging, computer tomography (CT) [1] [2] makes it possible to look into the interior of the human body. Its algorithmic behavior can be described by means of the Radon transform, which has been developed by Radon [5] in 1917, whereas CT itself has been introduced by Cormack in 1970. Numerous algorithms basing on the Radon transform have been developed for the reconstruction of images during the last twenty years. Most of these algorithms are working with continuous signals. In practice, the projection data is measured in discretized form. Hence, knowledge of the spectral properties is necessary to optimize the sampling procedure.

The Radon transform describes the relation between an image $g(x, y)$ and its associated projections $p(l, \Theta)$ under all angles Θ and is given by

$$p(l, \Theta) = p(-l, \Theta + \pi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(l \cos \Theta - s \sin \Theta, l \sin \Theta + s \cos \Theta) ds \quad (1)$$

where the image $g(x, y)$ is integrated along lines defined by $l = x \cos \Theta + y \sin \Theta$ for fixed rotation angle Θ and fixed l . The definition of coordinate systems and projections

Figure 1: Definition of coordinate systems and projections

is illustrated by means of figure (1). Since $p(l, \Theta)$ is a π -periodic function in the variable Θ , a corresponding Fourier transform doesn't exist. However we are able to develop the one-dimensional Fourier transform $P(j\omega_l, \Theta)$ with respect to l into a Fourier series with respect to Θ having the Fourier coefficients $P_n(j\omega_l)$.

In practice, the projections are measured for discretized values of l and Θ . Therefore, the bandwidth with respect to the l -variable of the projection signal has to be known in order to obtain information about the bandwidth of the reconstructed image. Obviously, we have to limit the size of images under consideration with respect to both variables x and y . However, a windowed (spatially limited) image has an infinite broad spectrum. Due to Shannons sampling theorem a perfect reconstruction is impossible in this situations and knowledge about the bandwidth of the projection signal and its relation to the spectrum of the underlying image is important for designing a reliable reconstruction algorithm.

A first attempt to solve this problem has been done by Paul A. Rattey [6] in 1981. In this work, the image is limited spatially and decomposed into a sum of weighted impulse functions. Afterwards the behavior of the individual impulses is analyzed separately. The spectrum of the projection signal $p(l, \Theta)$ is characterized by Bessel functions of the type

$$e^{-jn\Omega\alpha} e^{jn\frac{\pi}{2}} J_{-n}(\omega_l r_0), \quad (2)$$

where r_0 is the distance of the impulse under consideration from the origin and α is its angle with respect to the x -axis. In doing this, it is possible to estimate the bandwidth of the projection signal and to obtain information about the necessary sampling rate.

2 Analysis of a harmonic signal

In this paper an alternative approach is considered which is based on classical methods. We are investigating the two-dimensional spectral behavior of the projection signal $p(l, \Theta)$ if the image is represented by merely one cosine function, i.e.

$$g(x, y) = \cos(\omega_{x,0}x + \omega_{y,0}y), \quad (3)$$

where $\omega_{x,0}$ is the fixed frequency component in x -direction and $\omega_{y,0}$ is the fixed frequency component in y -direction. In a first step we compute the projection of the unlimited (not windowed) signal $g(x, y)$. Although this situation is only of theoretical interest it gives deep insight into the properties of the spectrum. We compute the one-dimensional Fourier transform $P(j\omega_l, \Theta)$ of $p(l, \Theta)$ with respect to l

$$P(j\omega_l, \Theta) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(l, \Theta) e^{-j\omega_l l} dl \quad (4)$$

and obtain the spectrum

$$P(j\omega_l, \Theta) = [\delta(\omega_l - \omega_{r,0} \cos(\Theta - \alpha_0)) + \delta(\omega_l + \omega_{r,0} \cos(\Theta - \alpha_0))] \cdot \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(\Theta - \alpha_0 - m\pi), \quad (5)$$

where $\omega_{r,0}$ and α_0 are the polarcoordinates respective to the cartesian point $[\omega_{x,0}, \omega_{y,0}]$. This function is π -periodic with respect to variable Θ and thus can be expanded into a Fourier series having the coefficients

$$P_n(j\omega_l) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} P(j\omega_l, \Theta) e^{-jn\frac{2\pi}{\pi}\Theta} d\Theta, \quad (6)$$

where $P_n(j\omega_l)$ is the sampled (with respect to ω_{Θ}) Fourier transform of one period of the projection signal $p(l, \Theta)$. This result is due to the fact, that generally the Fourier coefficients of a periodic function can be obtained by sampling the Fourier transform of one basic period of the signal. Invoking (5) we get the result

$$P_n(j\omega_l) = [\delta(\omega_l - \omega_{r,0}) + \delta(\omega_l + \omega_{r,0})] \cdot \frac{1}{\pi} e^{-j2n\alpha_0}. \quad (7)$$

Figure 2: A section of the spectral coefficients for $\omega_{r,0}a = 10\pi$

Obviously, these Fourier coefficients do not vanish with increasing index n (increasing frequency with respect to Θ), i.e. the signal cannot be considered to be band-limited. In order to be closer to real situations we analyse now the projection signal of a spatially limited image region having of dimension $2a \times 2a$. Using the same procedure as above, we are able to compute the spectrum $P(j\omega_l, \Theta)$ of the projection signal $p(l, \Theta)$ with respect to variable l

$$P(j\omega_l, \Theta) = \frac{\sin(\omega_{r,0}a \sin \varphi)}{\omega_{r,0} \sin \varphi} \cdot \left[\frac{\sin[a(\omega_l - \omega_{r,0} \cos \varphi)]}{\omega_l - \omega_{r,0} \cos \varphi} + \frac{\sin[a(\omega_l + \omega_{r,0} \cos \varphi)]}{\omega_l + \omega_{r,0} \cos \varphi} \right], \quad (8)$$

with $\varphi = \Theta - \alpha_0$. This function is π -periodic with respect to variable φ and we can expand it in a Fourier series having coefficients

$$P_n(j\omega_l) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} P(j\omega_l, \varphi + \alpha_0) e^{-j2n\varphi} d\varphi. \quad (9)$$

It is not possible to solve this integrals explicitly, hence they have to be computed by using numerical methods. An example of this result is shown in figure (2).

3 Bandwidth of the projection signal

The spectral behavior of the projection signal can be investigated by analysing the Fourier coefficients $P_n(j\omega_l)$. If we recall the result (7) for the unlimited case and compare it with figure 2 where an example for $P_n(j\omega_l)$ in the limited case is shown we can conclude the following. The object under consideration has to be spatially limited with respect to both variables x and y in order to achieve a decaying spectrum in ω_{Θ} -direction (frequency

variable associated with angular variable Θ). On the other hand, a spatially limited object causes an unlimited spectrum in ω_l -direction. In other words we cannot avoid aliasing errors in sampling the projection signal $p(l, \Theta)$ with respect to radial component l and angular variable Θ . However, it is possible to minimize these errors by defining an optimal sampling grid.

In analysing the infinitely extended spectrum we make use of Parseval's Theorem for the computation of the energy of the spectrum, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-a}^a \int_0^\pi |p(l, \Theta)|^2 d\Theta dl = \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \pi \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} |P_n(j\omega_l)|^2 d\omega_l. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The spectral energy is concentrated in a small domain around the origin. However, this result has to be interpreted carefully since the spectrum is rapidly decreasing in ω_l -direction. If the object under consideration consists of a harmonic signal of low frequency, the spectral energy is concentrated in a small domain. Conversely, if we have a high frequency harmonic signal, the spectral energy is distributed over a broad region. Consequently, amplitudes of spectral components can be much larger in the first case compared to the high frequency case. From the relation

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^\pi |P(j\omega_l, \Theta)|^2 d\Theta = \\ & \pi \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} |P_n(j\omega_l)|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

we obtain the whole energy for a fixed value of ω_l . If we compare it to the sum

$$\pi \sum_{n=-N}^N |P_n(j\omega_l)|^2 \quad (12)$$

for increasing values of N we can find an N_0 for which the missing terms $|P_{N_0+1}(j\omega_l)|^2 \dots$ can be neglected. In other words, N_0 defines the bandwidth in ω_Θ -direction. Empirical investigations led to the result

$$\Delta\omega_\Theta = (\omega_l a + 1) \quad (13)$$

as the bandwidth with respect to ω_Θ . Obviously, $\Delta\omega_\Theta$ depends on ω_l . Conversely, if we are interested in the bandwidth with respect to ω_l we expand the π -periodic (with respect to Θ) function $p(l, \Theta)$ in a Fourier series

with coefficients $p_n(l)$ and consider the energy

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-a}^a |p_n(l)|^2 dl = \\ & \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |P_n(j\omega_l)|^2 d\omega_l \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Similar considerations as above lead to the following results. The spectral energy decreases sufficiently fast for all harmonic frequencies $\omega_{r,0}$.

In the same manner as applied above we define the integral

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\omega_0}^{\omega_0} |P_n(j\omega_l)|^2 d\omega_l, \quad (15)$$

which is the energy in the band $\Delta\omega_l = \omega_0$. By evaluating empiric results obtained from the numeric solution of (9) we find a limit-frequency ω_0 for which the whole energy in the band above ω_0 can be neglected.

4 The sampling grid for projection data

First, let us assume that the object under consideration is approximately bandlimited with a cut-off frequency ω_g in both directions. The bandwidth of the spectrum of the corresponding projection signal $p(l, \Theta)$ is given by

$$\Delta\omega_\Theta = (\omega_l a + 1), \quad (16)$$

which obviously depends on ω_l , and

$$\Delta\omega_l = \omega_g + \frac{5\pi}{a}. \quad (17)$$

Large aliasing errors can be avoided by adding $5\pi/a$ to the limit-frequency ω_g . This value has been determined experimentally by solving (9) numerically. Based on these results, we compute the maximally admissible values for the sampling periods T_Θ and T_l for the variables Θ and l

$$T_\Theta \leq \frac{\pi}{\omega_g a + 5\pi + 1} \quad (18)$$

and

$$T_l \leq \frac{\pi}{\omega_g + \frac{5\pi}{a}}, \quad (19)$$

where (18) has been derived from (16) by setting $\omega_l = \omega_g + \frac{5\pi}{a}$ which is the maximal value for ω_l (compare (17)). Obviously, the bandlimitations of the spectrum of the projection signal are mainly determined by the limitfrequency ω_g of the spectrum of the object signal and the projection distance $2a$. In view of (18) and (19) the least number of sampling points is given by

$$NM = \left\lceil \frac{2\omega_g a + 10\pi}{\pi} \right\rceil ([\omega_g a + 5\pi] + 1), \quad (20)$$

Figure 3: The periodical spectrum of the projection data after progressive sampling (left) and the corresponding spectrum after interlaced sampling (right).

where $[\cdot]$ denotes the integer operator, getting the nearest integer not less than the argument. For progressive sampling the corresponding sampling matrix is given by

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} T_l & 0 \\ 0 & T_\Theta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

The resulting spectrum of the sampled signal is periodic where the periodicity is described by the matrix

$$\mathbf{\Omega} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{2\pi}{T_l} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{2\pi}{T_\Theta} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (22)$$

with

$$\mathbf{\Omega}^t = 2\pi\mathbf{T}^{-1}. \quad (23)$$

Figure (3) is a standardized view of this periodical spectrum. The white regions represent domains bearing no relevant information. In order to utilize the whole spectral area in a more effective manner we choose a different spectral matrix

$$\mathbf{\Omega} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\pi}{T_l} & \frac{\pi}{T_l} \\ \frac{\pi}{T_\Theta} & -\frac{\pi}{T_\Theta} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (24)$$

For this kind of sampling we have to decrease the sampling period T_Θ , since the bandwidth of the spectrum in ω_Θ -direction is not zero around $\omega_l = 0$ (16). Doing this, we get a periodic spectrum without empty regions in between as shown in figure (3). The new sampling matrix can be computed by using (23)

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} T_l & T_l \\ T_\Theta & -T_\Theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

with

$$T_l \leq \frac{2a}{\left\lceil \frac{2\omega_g a + 10\pi}{\pi} \right\rceil}, \quad T_\Theta \leq \frac{\pi}{([\omega_g a + 5\pi] + 2)} \quad (26)$$

where $[\cdot]$ denotes the integer operator, getting the nearest integer not less than the argument. The resulting sampling grid is known as an interlaced grid or hexagonal sampling grid. The use of this interlaced grid decreases the total number of necessary sampling points to

$$NM = \frac{\left\lceil \frac{2\omega_g a + 10\pi}{\pi} \right\rceil ([\omega_g a + 5\pi] + 2)}{2}. \quad (27)$$

5 Conclusions

In this paper we have reviewed the spectral properties of projection signals in order to derive conditions for choosing optimal sampling grids. It has been shown that bandlimitations of the spectrum of the continuous projection signal $p(l, \Theta)$ are necessary conditions for a unique reconstruction of objects from sampled versions of $p(l, \Theta)$.

It has been shown that the analysis of the two-dimensional spectrum of $p(l, \Theta)$ is the key to obtain deep insight into the behavior of sampled projection signals. The results are similar to those reported in [6], however, in the present paper the sampling of the l -variable (radial component) has also been taken into account. It had been important to discuss the behavior of low-frequency and high-frequency object signals separately. As a consequence, the relevant bandwidth with respect to ω_l of the projection signal $p(l, \Theta)$, which is used for defining sampling periods, has to be enlarged in comparison to the work in [6]. Since the bandwidth of the projection signal in both frequency directions depends on the limit-frequency ω_g of the spectrum of the object under consideration, the sampling of both variables l and Θ has to be modified. Otherwise aliasing errors can occur and lead to significant errors in the reconstructed image.

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